

Study on Effect of Yoga and Meditation in Reduction of Stress in Diabetic and Hypertensive Patients

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Abstract:

Stress is a response to a physical threat or psychological distress that generates a host of chemical and hormonal reactions in the body. As a part of the adaptive response to stress, various body systems such as the autonomic, cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, and immune systems may be affected. Yoga and meditation help therapeutically and promotes physical and mental health. Study group of patients & individuals were enrolled from both MGM hospital and International Sahaja Yoga Meditation and Research Centre. So it may be concluded that Sahaja yoga meditation if included as part of regular treatment regimen along with routine medication it can lead improvement in quality of life by reducing stress and thus prevent complications of Diabetes mellitus & Hypertension.

Keywords: T2DM -Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, LDL - Low Density Lipoprotein, HDL-High Density Lipoprotein, TG- Triglyceride, HbA1c - Glycated Hemoglobin, Sahaja Yoga.

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Introduction

Stress is a response to a physical threat or psychological distress that generates a host of chemical and hormonal reactions in the body. As a part of the adaptive response to stress, various body systems such as the autonomic, cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, and immune systems may be affected.

Diabetes mellitus is becoming increasingly prevalent and magnifies the risk of cardiovascular complications and shares several risk factors in common with CAD. Hypertension is a major contributor to the cardiovascular morbidity and mortality in industrialized countries and is rapidly increasing in developing countries like India.

Yoga and meditation help therapeutically and promotes physical and mental health. Because of the increasing burden of the lifestyle diseases and potential to prevent them, efforts are required for promotion of stress relaxation programs and diabetes screening programs.

Increasing awareness of risk factors and how to prevent these should be emphasized in the population. It is believed that regular practice of yoga and meditation brings about a decrease in

stress levels and improved antioxidant status. Sahaja Yoga a unique method of meditation is the state of self-realization produced by kundalini awakening and is accompanied by the experience of thoughtless awareness or mental silence.

Materials & Methods

The aim of this study was to assess the effect of yoga and meditation in reduction of stress in patients with Diabetes mellitus and Hypertension. Study group of patients & individuals were enrolled from both MGM hospital and International Sahaja Yoga Meditation and Research Centre. Informed consent was taken from all the patients. All questionnaires and Investigations which are mentioned were done at MGM Medical College. The Biochemical parameters such as, fasting blood sugar (FBS), HbA1c, cortisol was determined. The MDA (malondialdehyde), SOD (superoxide dismutase), and Nitric oxide activities were measured for antioxidant status. All parameters were performed in the Department of Biochemistry, MGM Medical College.

Results and Discussion:

Table 1: Comparison of Diabetic hypertensive patients (with & without yoga)

Parameter	Group	Mean	SD	t-stat	p-value
Glucose (mg/dl)	Diabetic without yoga	183.13	61.53	3.42	0.0001***
	Diabetic with yoga	123.13	28.44		
HbA1c (%)	Diabetic without yoga	7.7	1.88	2.69	0.011*
	Diabetic with yoga	6.16	1.17		
Cortisol (nmol/L)	Diabetic without yoga	406.51	75.95	3.11	0.004**
	Diabetic with yoga	332.96	50.72		
MDA (nmol/ml)	Diabetic without yoga	4.45	0.69	5.31	0.0001***
	Diabetic with yoga	3.17	0.622		
SOD (Unit/ml)	Diabetic without yoga	0.723	0.66	-5.738	0.10001***
	Diabetic with yoga	1.962	(1513)		
NO (um01/L)	Diabetic without yoga	32.5	21.022	-6.262	0.0001***
	Diabetic with yoga	86.66	26.077		
SBP(mmHg)	Diabetic without yoga	137.6	10.11	4.35	0.0001***
	Diabetic with yoga	122.9	8.2		
DBP(mmHg)	Diabetic without yoga	90.9	7.7	2.84	0.008**
	Diabetic with yoga	84.26	4.77		

Fig-1 Chart shows comparison of MDA mean in different groups

Fig-2 Chart shows comparison of SOD mean in different groups

Fig-3 Chart shows comparison of NO mean in different groupes

Fig-4 Chart shows comparison of Glucose mean in different groupes

Fig-5 Chart shows comparison of HbA1c mean in different groupes

Fig-6 Chart shows comparison of Cortisol mean in different groups

In this study it was observed that: MDA level is decreased significantly and levels of SOD and NO were increased significantly in diabetic and diabetic hypertensive individuals after Sahaja yoga meditation. A significant level of decrease in FBG & HbA1C was obtained in diabetic and diabetic hypertensive individuals after Sahaja yoga meditation. We also observed that cortisol level, a stress marker was found to be decreased significantly in subjects after Sahaja yoga meditation. The study was undertaken to determine serum levels of antioxidants like superoxide dismutase (SOD) activities in diabetic and diabetic hypertensive patients, who were undergoing Sahaja yoga meditation; we found that there was significant improvement in these patients as compared to the diabetic and diabetic hypertensive patients, who were not undergoing Sahaja yoga meditation. The levels of these antioxidants gradually increased after Sahaja yoga meditation in healthy, Diabetic & Diabetic hypertensive subjects.

The level of MDA, a marker of lipid peroxidation was decreased in healthy as well as in diabetic and diabetic hypertensive individuals after Sahaja yoga meditation. There is also reduction in Fasting Blood Glucose & HbA1C in control, Diabetic & Diabetic hypertensive patients after Sahaja yoga meditation.

Also, there is improvement in stress marker like Cortisol in control subjects, Diabetic & Diabetic hypertensive patients, so it may be said that, Sahaja yoga meditation if included as part of regular treatment regimen along with routine medication it can lead improvement of quality of life by reducing stress and thus prevent complications of Diabetes mellitus & Hypertension.

Conclusion

So it may be concluded that Sahaja yoga meditation if included as part of regular treatment regimen along with routine medication it can lead improvement in quality of life by reducing stress and thus prevent complications of Diabetes mellitus & Hypertension.

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